

ROLE OF EDUCATION IN PARADIGM SHIFT

*Dr Shalini Singh

**Apoorva Tyagi

Abstract

Education is basic and important need of developed and modern society not only to get a white collar job but also for an ideal future. Now a days the main purpose of education is to change the concept of acquiring marks and grades only. For this change the new paradigm shifting towards constructivism and Continuous Comprehensive Evolution (CCE) pattern and new technologies like Information and Communication Technology (ICT) based education programme is needed. Role of education is to give continuous comprehensive education for all caste, religion, women and special need children. Through this research paper the researcher wants to focus on the role of education in shifting its paradigm. The researcher expects that this research paper would certainly be fruitful in shifting paradigm of education and provide new horizons to education.

Keywords - Elementary Education, Secondary Level of Education, Senior Secondary Level of Education, Higher Education.

Introduction

Now a days, there is a very broad change in the field of education across the country. The last decades of the 20th century have brought the concept of education only for the sake of employment but it was the first step towards the new dawn of education. In 21st century the Information and Communication Technology is one of the achievement in the field of education for paradigm shift. In this century education not only for employment purposive but also a character making perspective. The paradigm shift from behaviorism to constructivism also leads to the professionalization of teaching. From the paradigm shifting in education there are the objectives of education on each level are also modified.

Paradigm Shift at Elementary Level

Elementary education is the foundation stone of the entire educational system. It is for students of class 1st to 5th. The national curriculum framework of school education 2000 (NCFSE 2000) therefore attempts to enrich the curriculum at elementary stage of school by modern approaches reducing the burden of irrelevant and incomprehensible material. A major shift at the upper primary stage in the teaching of sciences and social sciences. Each has to be taught as an integrated subject. The new school curriculum also give attention to the education to children of special need groups backward classes of society, women, rural, poor, tribal, minorities as well as to the disabled.

Another major thrust is that the content of education be rooted in Indian thought and experiences and remain open to ideas from outside. The NCFSE 2000 highlights education in human values as an integral part of curriculum for all subjects at all stage of school education. Achieving (MLL) Minimum Learning Level is get another concern reflected in the school curriculum framework for elementary school stage. The paradigm shift of elementary education have to orient to MLL in terms of performance capabilities of learners, translating them to specific learning outcomes in the form of competencies. There is a clear picture of paradigm shift of elementary education as below:

*Assistant Professor, Department of Education, V.M.L.G. College, Ghaziabad

**M.Ed Student, V.M.L.G. College, Ghaziabad

Paradigm Shift at Elementary Level

Secondary Level

Secondary Level is the backbone of the body of entire education system. It extends over standard 9th to 10th. This is the final stage of ten year school and is meant for general education for all and so it will have a common curriculum. For orientation of students additional selective courses and pre-vocational courses should be introduced.

The use of ICT on this level is started from initial stage .Audio visual aids and teaching through technologies is commonly used at this level of education.

The objectives of paradigm shifts in education on secondary level are s follows-

- To maintain the continuity of elementary education students should get opportunity to choose subjects of their choices.
- To train them in the use of ICT, its advantages disadvantages and safeguards should be told.
- To develop the attitude love towards their country heritage, culture and its contribution to the world and to inculcate a sense of national pride and identity should be explained.
- To create awareness of environmental protection and need to maintain an ecological balance should be maintained.
- To develop the peaceful minds importance to peace of mind Meditation, Yoga and other spiritual activity should be provided.

Paradigm Shift at Secondary Level

Senior Secondary Level

Senior secondary level is the highest level of school education. On this level students decide their future plans studies of higher level professions. So the objectives of on this level with paradigm shift will be -

- To develop an acceptable desired perspective about academic stream and understanding of this nature purpose and philosophy.
- To guide learners and prepare them for self study , independent learning , critical thinking , conceptualization ,self evaluation of their own performance and derive knowledge information from ICT and Mass Media.
- To develop patriotic feeling national consciousness social cohesion communal harmony and universal brotherhood.
- To impart enriched vocational education which is essential for success in competitive and open market economy.

Objectives of Paradigm Shifts at Senior Secondary Level

Higher Studies Level

At the college level a student wants to lead an independent life by vocational and social adjustment. Therefore, the categories of objectives at college and higher study level can be presented and arranged under five categories covering at the courses and disciplines.

These are as follows-

- Providing Knowledge of essential facts to students.
- Understanding of essential principles, concepts, trends and generalizations
- Ability and Willingness to make functional and objectives use of knowledge and understanding in thinking.
- Ability to develop broader, sharper or deeper, interests, appreciations and value with respect to the discipline.
- Development of essential skills, selected specially to the field of study like findings, shifting, summarizing, evaluating, organizing and checking data and sources.
- Communicating by writing, reporting, discussing, and visualizing.
- Developing certain minor skills essential for mastering other skills.

Conclusion

Thus it is clear that a paradigm shift in education is change of thoughts, objectives and mind set about the education system. In 20th century the concept of education were based on theoretical foundation but after 21st century these concepts are based on practical foundation. In 20th century education was based on the traditional and dependable conditions at every level of education but in 21st century the education became liberal and modern. Now these days student are not fully dependent upon bookish knowledge and traditional type of examination processes. Their knowledge is futuristic, applicable in present condition and self evaluated.

In social context of the paradigm shifts from present knowledge to futuristic knowledge there is not only of social growth of an individual but it is indicate the growth of society. In new context of education a child expresses, explore, and establish himself by own interests and aptitude. Here is the consolidation table showing objectives of paradigm shift in education at all levels before and after 21st century.

Educational Aspects	Before 21 st Century	After 21 st Century
	Focus on rearrangement of knowledge General	Focus on creation of knowledge.

Educational Objectives	objectives of knowledge Personal Growth Social Growth Ability to know Content Based Activities Teacher's dictation Dependent individual	Specific objectives of education Personality growth Growth of society Ability to Do Need based activities Teacher's ideas Self-Reliant individual
Teachers Selection	Past knowledge	Future knowledge
Content Selection	only information acquisition	Application of knowledge
Curriculum	Collective and generalized	Individualized and selective
Evaluation	Based on knowledge	Based on learning
Methodology of Learning	Traditional methods and techniques	Modern and ICT based methods of teaching
Performance of Learner	Teacher Dependant	Self-Reliance

In short we can conclude that there is vivid scenario of paradigm shift in terms of objectives at each level of education .Then researcher have established new horizon of education through the research paper and hope it would be helpful as well as fruitful for future generation to understand change during eras of time.

References

1. Madhavan & Banerji Rukmini, "The challenge of achieving desirable levels of learning in elementary education," Journal of governance, July 2012.
2. Aggarwal Radha and Indrani, "Influence of activity based integrated curriculum of environmental studies of grade III on academic achievement of the students." Naval shodh June, 2010.
3. Alfred, Richard and Patricia Carter, Reaching for the Future, Ann Arbor, MI: Consortium for Community College Development, 1997.
4. Barr, Robert B. and John Tagg, "From Teaching to Learning: A New Paradigm for Undergraduate Education," Change 27, (6).
5. Beichner, Robert J. and Jeffrey M. Saul, "Introduction to the SCALEUP (Student-Centered Activities for Large Enrollment Undergraduate Programs) Project, Paper submitted to the Proceedings of the International School of Physics, "Enrico Fermi," Varenna, Italy, (July 2003).